

HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT AGEMERA

by

Jari Joutsenvaara¹, Marko Holma¹, Georg Meissner², Taras Matselyukh³,
Francisco Gutierrez³ and Leena Suopajarvi⁴

¹ University of Oulu, Kerttu Saalasti Institute, Pajatie 5, FI-86800 Nivala, Finland

E-mail: jari.joutsenvaara@oulu.fi

² Institute of Mining and Special Civil Engineering, TU Bergakademie Freiberg, Germany

³ OPT/NET B.V, Bergen, Netherlands

⁴ University of Lapland, Faculty of Social Sciences, P.O. Box 122, FI-96101 Rovaniemi, Finland

The digital and green transition aims to bring Europe as a NetZero CO₂ producer by 2050. The need for raw materials is increasing to reach these goals, especially in electrification of mobility, metal processing, renewable energy production and hydrogen economy. Some material needs can be met with recycling, some by substituting current critical raw materials (CRMs) with more abundant materials, but primary raw materials are still needed to meet the demand. However, resourcing must be done responsibly, including people, the environment and the economy. The EU-funded AGEMERA project studies the CRM potential within Europe and Zambia, developing novel AGEMERA AI-aided platforms, exploration technologies, and new tools for social sciences to study people's perceptions of mining and exploration. The project also raises awareness of how metals and raw materials are present in our everyday lives and where the materials come from. Responsible sourcing is also one of the EU's goals. The project's technologies and studies are piloted in five trial areas in Europe and one in Zambia. The project and its status are presented in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

The European Union's green and digital transition goals are crucial in advancing European decarbonisation efforts. These significant changes involve shifting to electric transportation, moving from carbon-based energy production to renewable sources, and innovating new technologies and strategies for the efficient distribution of clean energy (Muench et al. 2022). However, achieving these goals faces a notable challenge – manufacturing environmentally-friendly technologies requires substantial amounts of various metals and minerals.

While recycling initiatives, circular economic models, and research-driven substitution of critical materials contribute partially to the supply chain, their impact falls short compared to the projected future demands (Grohol & Veeh 2023). A consensus acknowledges the urgent need for increased raw material production. Additionally, essential raw materials are classified as “critical” due to economic

and supply availability factors. Currently, the EU's native supply of several primary CRMs represents a fraction, less than 3%, underscoring the Union's significant dependence on imports from countries like China, Russia, and South Africa.

Given the changing global landscape, the EU has introduced the Critical Raw Materials Act, aiming to, by 2030, reduce reliance on any single country as a primary source of certain raw materials (seeking less than 65% at any stage of the processing from any single country, having at least 10% of European consumption from domestic extraction). More importantly, the Union's recycling capacity should be able to produce at least 15% of the Union's annual consumption of strategic raw materials (European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs 2023). Strategies such as boosting domestic production and diversifying the supply chain are perceived as potential solutions to enhance Europe's autonomy concerning raw materials. Among these initiatives, the AGEMERA project, funded through Horizon Europe, focuses on refining mineral system models, creating innovative tools for studying mineral exploration and mining perceptions, assisting SMEs in their mineral exploration technology development, and promoting awareness of this twin transition (Holma et al. 2022, 2023, Holma 2023).

THE PROJECT GOALS

The project encompasses several key objectives and intermediary outcomes to advance our understanding of geological and mineralogical processes while introducing innovative methodologies. AGEMERA's geological objectives are designed to enhance the understanding and exploration of CRMs through a systematic approach encompassing literature review, field data collection, data synthesis, computer-based modelling, and mineral system model development. The project examines not only surface geology but also the entire crust and upper mantle, with a focus on structures influencing mineralisation. A key strategy involves gathering new field data to fill gaps in geochemical and mineral-chemistry information. This refines computer models to understand CRM distribution in chosen countries better. By combining all data, AGEMERA seeks to provide insights into the location and reasons behind CRM occurrence, identifying previously overlooked areas for exploration. The ultimate aim is to contribute significantly to sustainable mining in the EU.

From the technological side, the project focuses on novel, non-invasive mineral exploration techniques that are environmentally and socially responsible. To this end, the project develops inventive methodologies that embrace innovation and sustainability. These methodologies encompass muography, microseismic surveys, and drone-based electromagnetic surveying. Each approach holds promise in offering insights into subsurface mineral deposits without resorting to intrusive practices.

The project's success hinges on creating a comprehensive data platform. This platform, powered by the AGEMERA AI engine, utilises Artificial Intelligence Knowledge Packs (AI KPs). These AI KPs work through the AGEMERA AI platform's backend to process different data types, such as satellite images, mineral exploration data and mining-related information. They manage tasks like cleaning up data, improving images, and conducting AI-driven analyses. This technology allows closing in on specific regions of interest and gathering customer and satellite data to provide valuable insights about mineral mining sites in different countries.

Once published, the user-friendly AGEMERA AI GUI, based on natural language, is accessible on the cloud for easy utilisation.

In tandem with technical advancements, the AGEMERA project acknowledges the pivotal role of a social license to operate (SLO) and social acceptance (SA) within mineral exploration and mining. The project emphasises understanding local contexts, as highlighted by Jason Prno (Prno 2013). To address this, the University of Lapland and its partners designed an online questionnaire piloted in Northern Finland during Q1 of 2023, exploring how diverse operating practices and local conditions impact the mineral industry's acceptability on both local and societal scales. After analysing and adapting the key learnings, the survey will be conducted across AGEMERA partners' research areas in various countries in 2023–2024.

Beyond the scientific and societal dimensions, the project looks into the importance of raw materials to our society, economy, and individual lives. The project promotes responsible resource management, consumption and recycling by enhancing awareness of CRMs' role in our day-to-day existence. These subjects will be addressed through courses at higher educational institutions, public events, and, later in the project, through developing a serious game focused on CRMs and their role in modern society. The project advocates for utilising the United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC) and the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS) as pivotal tools for guiding future experts in the field. This integration of international frameworks underscores the project's commitment to aligning its objectives with broader sustainable development initiatives. (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe 2021, Hokka et al. 2020)

THE STUDY AREAS

The project's selected study areas are variably studied using conventional field geological and laboratory methods, novel technologies developed and applied in the project, or combining both approaches. All sites were selected either for their confirmed presence of CRMs or their potential to contain them. The chosen locations capture the breadth of the mining lifecycle by presenting three early-stage projects (one in each in Finland, Spain and Zambia), five current mining sites (one in each in Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Poland and Spain) and two historical mining sites (in Germany). Some of these locations are also studied by applying SLO and SLE research techniques. Geologically speaking, the areas range from the Early Proterozoic Peräpohja belt in Finland to much younger geological terranes (e.g., the Panagyurishte region of the Apuseni-Banat-Timok-Srednogorie belt in Bulgaria; (Peytcheva et al. 2022)).

The deposits in the selected study areas fall into a diverse range of genetic types: 1) orogenic gold enriched in cobalt in Finland; 2) stratabound copper and silver enriched in cobalt, zinc, nickel, molybdenum and vanadium in Poland; 3) karst bauxite in Bosnia-Herzegovina; 4) porphyry copper and epithermal gold in Bulgaria, locally associated with platinum group elements; 5) volcanogenic massive sulphide deposits, characterised by nickel-copper-cobalt, in Spain; 6) lithium and tin greisens in Germany; and 7) sedimentary rock-hosted manganese in Zambia. In addition, the geological team has also reviewed the possibilities of studying metasomatically enriched lithium mineralisation in Spain and poorly outcropping iron oxide copper gold mineralisation in Bulgaria. Among the most notable deposits studied in the project are the Assarel open-pit porphyry copper mine and the Lubin underground Kupferschiefer-type copper mine. Regarding the

technologies to be developed in AGEMERA, passive seismic methods are applied in Bosnia–Herzegovina, Spain and Poland, airborne fixed–wing drone geophysics (UAV EM) in Finland and Zambia, and muography in Poland, Bosnia–Herzegovina and Bulgaria.

THE CURRENT STATUS OF THE AGEMERA PROJECT

The AGEMERA project has completed approximately one year of its three–year duration. Novel technologies have been successfully deployed in various trial areas, marking a significant step forward. The introduction of initial university courses, integrated into existing curricula, has already taken place, while the development of new courses is actively underway. A pivotal pilot questionnaire, utilising a softGIS approach, has been launched to gauge public perceptions, aspirations, and concerns regarding mineral exploration and mining, particularly in regions of personal significance. The ongoing analysis of the questionnaire responses is providing valuable insights. AGEMERA AI has showcased its prowess in seamlessly integrating diverse datasets, encompassing the outputs of the novel technologies developed within the project.

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